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AIRBORNE
LABORATORY

Calibration by comparison of Buck CR2 optical dew-point hygrometer

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Instrument under test: Buck CR2 219-M

Reference instrument: MBW 973-L S/N 18-0719

Reference instrument calibration:

NPL Certificate Ref 2022060331. Quartic calibration applied, coefficients [-8.39017E-03, 1.00080E-00, 4.66036E-05, 1.28770E-06, 1.87000E-08]

Calibration procedure:

A Michell Instruments DG2 is used to generate a flow of air of a fixed dewpoint, which is delivered to the hygrometers via stainless steel ¼ inch internal diameter tubing. The flow is split between the MBW 973-L reference instrument and the instrument under test. The test hygrometer mirror is cleaned beforehand. For each calibration point, which are no more than 20°C intervals between -50 and +20°C, the instruments are allowed to stabilise before readings of mirror temperature are recorded over no less than 10 minutes for mirror temperatures below -25°C, and no less than 5 minutes at temperatures above -25°C. These readings are logged over RS232 for each instrument, and a mean and standard deviation calculated for each calibration point. Should the calibration show a lack of agreement within uncertainty between the MBW 973-L and the Buck CR2, a calibration curve is generated and applied to the Buck CR2 output in processing.

Results:

MBW 973-L 18-0719	Buck CR2 211-M	CR2 Standard deviation
-49.97	-49.18	0.09
-38.64	-38.56	0.09
-29.44	-29.16	0.05
-13.10	-14.43	0.05
-5.66	-6.21	0.05
4.72	4.85	0.03
19.17	19.24	0.02

Quartic calibration coefficients to be applied to Buck CR2 output in processing:

[-1.96849E-06, - 1.26036E-04, + 4.51025E-04, + 1.07161E+00 - 2.95262E-01]